

Problems and Prospects of Agricultural Development in Muzaffarpur District

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Abstract

Agriculture reigns supreme in the socio-economic and cultural life of India in general and Bihar in particular agriculture contributes about 23% of the total G.D.P. of India, but in Bihar it stills contributes more than 65% of the state's total G.D.P. Muzaffarpur district is 4th largest district of North Bihar and here importance of agriculture is almost the same as in Bihar as a whole. Still more than 87% people of the district are dependent on the fate and fortune of agricultural development. Prospects of agricultural development are limitless but problems in its way of development are immensely acute and vast.

Keywords

Problems, Prospects, Agricultural, Development, Muzaffarpur, District.

Introduction

Economy of Muzaffarpur district, famous for lichi fruits and wholesale textiles market in Bihar is predominately rural and agriculture. In the absence of industrial landscape amidst surplus available raw materials the district behaves like an orphan and hapless child. M.S. Swaminathan, a well-known agronomist's observation may be quoted "Nothing can move until and unless agriculture moves and agriculture cannot move until and unless water is put to use at the time of requirement for the growth of crops". Despite of such an overwhelming importance of agriculture in shaping the destiny of our people, agriculture has been remaining the subject of utter neglect and biasness. This is why the place of our agricultural development has been extremely sluggish.

Objective of study

In this article it has been tried to pin-point problems of development of agricultural land in Muzaffarpur and its remedial measures.

Review of Literature

Problems faced by agriculture

It is an acknowledged fact that in a monsoonal land there is an intricate relationship between crops and water. Here agriculture is both way adversely impacted in case of over-sufficiency and over deficiency of water. Distribution pattern of monsoon rainfall is very very uneven in relation to space and time. In such a grim situation management of water is so much important to crops as blood to our body. Unfortunately, problems related to water supply and availability loom large on the horizon of agriculture. The average annual receipt of rainfall (70 years average) in Bihar and Muzaffarpur is 120 cm and 112 cm respectively. This amount of rainfall is almost sufficient for proper Growth of plants without meaningful support by artificial watering. Agricultural practices are a continual process going throughout the year and year after year (sugarcane, banana etc.). It is an irony of fate that distributional pattern of rainfall in space and time context is extremely erratic and whimsical in nature. This is why sufficiency and deficiency becomes irrelevant for crop cultivation. Here scientific management of water becomes urgent need. C.D.B's located in South and Western parts of the district receive less rainfall than the northern and eastern parts of the district. Hence water management for the entire district may not the same.

Analysis

Water & crop management

The success of irrigated agriculture depends on the extent to which the water requirements of crops can be met. For maximizing agricultural production of an area, the adoption of suitable cropping pattern is of utmost importance. The planning and design of irrigation system is inextricably connected with the requirement of water for crops, as it is only correct determination of such requirement that can ensure the best use of the limited supplies of the utilizable water resources of a region. If water is appreciably less than the need for proper growth and maturity of a crop, the yield becomes poor both in quantity and quality. On the other hand, if excessive watering is given, damage both to crop as well as to determine the correct dosage of irrigation treatment both in quantum

and frequency required by the different crops that can be grown economically with the help of artificial irrigation in the tracts served or to be served by an irrigation project.

In the absence of artificial irrigation, the cropping pattern depends mainly on rainfall. As, in Bihar, rainfall is mainly confined to the monsoon season, the principal crop grown in the comparatively low land areas would be paddy and in the uplands it would be maize, marua, oat, barley, gram, biaseed, sweet potato, etc. In the dry weather, crops like khesari, peas, linseed may be grown in the medium and low land and mustard, barley, etc. in the up land.

Once the assured artificial irrigation is introduced, the cropping pattern would change depending on climatic factors, soil and sub-soil characteristics, pattern of availability of artificial irrigation, economics value of the different crops, etc. The water requirements of each crop are different and for the optimum utilization of the water resources consistent with the economic needs of the people, it would be necessary to devise crop patterns for different regions depending on the availability of water during the period of growth of each such crop, soil characteristics, climatic factors such as rainfall, etc., normally anticipated during the period, the market value of the crops grown, cost of inputs required, etc.

Any irrigation project has to be planned, designed and constructed in accordance with the cropping pattern that would appear, at the time, to be most beneficial with the cropping pattern that would appear, at the time, to be most beneficial to the cultivators of the area, whilst utilizing, to the maximum extent possible, the quantities of water that would be available during different times of the year.

To achieve best results, co-ordination between the Agriculture Department and the Irrigation Department in evaluating the water requirements and fixing the cropping pattern, commensurate with the water available for irrigation at different seasons of the year is essential. To be realistic, the cropping pattern in an irrigation command would depend on various factors such as

1. nature of soil
2. topography of the area
3. climatic condition
4. sub-soil water table and its drainability, etc. but principally on the availability of irrigation water at critical periods of irrigation demand during the different seasons.

Prior to the introduction of the high-yielding varieties farmers grew mainly timely fixed Aman paddy which requires irrigation at the critical flowering stage towards the end of September and beginning of October coinciding with period of Hasta (Hathia) Nakshatra. The traditional irrigation systems have been designed mainly to provide supplemental irrigation to paddy, the principal kharif crop of the state. The common practice in irrigated field was to take a Para crop like khesari, masoor, etc., from the paddy fields. Wheat was seldom grown in the same field after harvest of kharif paddy. The situation has completely changed with the introduction of the high-yielding varieties and the multiple cropping programmes. High-yielding periodically fixed paddy is replacing the timely fixed.

A man paddy and a short duration high-yielding variety of wheat is being raised on the same land by progressive farmers after harvesting of paddy. A third crop of summer paddy is being grown in areas in which irrigation is available in summer.

In fact, the cropping pattern in irrigated areas is dictated by the demand for the crop in the market and its price and not on availability of water on the suitability of the soil for the particular crop. While the Bihar Agriculture Directorate looks to the economics of the farmers and the need of the consumers, adequate attention has not been given so far to the availability of water for irrigation. It is not uncommon to find farmer putting in substantial areas under high-yielding varieties or summer paddy on the advice of the agriculture experts without taking note of the availability of water for irrigation. The cropping pattern in areas with limited water resources follows the usual paddy-paddy – wheat cycle. It is not always realised that even in a major irrigation project the cropping pattern has to take into account the factors like, the nature of the land, availability of water for irrigation and drainage facilities.

Such a cropping pattern can be evolved jointly by agricultural and irrigation experts. The ideal would be to prescribe a cropping pattern for each individual farmer, and for each individual field in the command areas of the irrigation projects, which may be difficult to achieve, it should, however, be possible to divide the irrigated area into different zones depending on the availability of water and drainage facilities and to further classify the lands in each zone into different groups and prescribe different crop rotations for each of these group in each of these zones. While it may be difficult to enforces the cropping

patterns through legislation many of the farmers may be willing to adopt the prescribed cropping pattern if they are convinced that these are the most economical. If the farmers understand that while the quantity of water a farmer is likely to receive for a particular field, though inadequate, for paddy can give him a bumper crop, he would gradually switch on to the prescribed cropping pattern. Therefore, it is quite desirable to design crop Cafeteria to show the farmer the best return he can get from his land by following a particular pattern.

Thus, the adoption of proper cropping pattern is of utmost importance which should suit the irrigation schedule. In fact, improved management of water and crop can probably help in increasing food supplies, raising agricultural income, and improving rural living conditions. It is, therefore, suggested that experts in agriculture, horticulture, animal husbandry and irrigation may jointly evolve cropping pattern for different regions and for different types of lands in each region and make them available to the farmers. Intensive research and extension education programmes in crop and water-management should also be taken up in different regions.

Conservation irrigation

To a farmer, 'conservation irrigation' can mean saving of water resulting in irrigation of larger areas with the available water- supply, control of erosion, better crop yields, lower production costs and assurance of continued productivity from his irrigated land. Conservation irrigation is required to ensure high agricultural production without either waste of water or deterioration and waste of soil. It means using cropping, irrigation and cultural practices that maintain the land in permanent agriculture with optimum yields. It can also mean a start towards the final solution of alkali problems.

water-logging and numerous other evils. Careless handling and negligent waste of irrigation water is responsible for many grave difficulties which now confront irrigated agriculture, as waste water can lead to waste land.

To attain maximum production per unit of water, a comprehensive strategy is needed for the conservation and development of our water resources. The absence of a coordinated strategy or faulty planning can lead to a waste of resources, and impose a severe limitation on the benefits which might otherwise have been derived from them. To obtain optimum benefits for increased agricultural production, judicious use of water has to be made in the light of results of research already available and also of further research which must be carried out. A number of works for the utilization of the run-off of the river flows of a number of rivers and torrents by diversion through irrigation channels into cultivated lands have been or are being carried out in Bihar. However, little has been done so far for the conservation and utilization of the flows that find their way into the sea, mainly during the monsoon season.

Beside these problems this district faces many other problems such as transport bottleneck, capital crunch, ill-agriculture marketing yards, no scientific storage facilities like Godowns, cold storage etc, non-functioning, price mechanism facilities, non-availability of HYV seeds and chemical fertilizers, fragmented and tiny plot-holding chakvandi process non-functional, non-availability of fruit-processing industries no viable support to harness solar energy and building bio-gas chambers etc. A fortuitous combination of these drawbacks have adverse bearings on the developments of agriculture.

Conclusion

The study area has brilliant future for agricultural development an progress, but in current practices major drawbacks are visible which have been adversely affecting it. If aforesaid problems are reversed by suitable measures, our agriculture is more than sufficient to export agro-products in huge quantity. Our soils are extremely fertile and homogenous. Water table has been very high it means that we have enough under-ground water potential. Floods can be contained by diverting water from one river to other. By increasing productivity per unit area of land, production may go up very high. Biharis are very labourious. proper facilities and marketing facilities will overturn our agriculture from down gear to up-gear.

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